

Polarographic Studies of Mixed Complexes of Cadmium(II) with Amino Acids and Pyridoxine (Vitamin B₆)

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Ternary complexes of cadmium(II) with amino acids (alanine, glycine, glutamic acid, serine and threonine) and pyridoxine have been studied polarographically at 30° and at a constant ionic strength $\mu = 1.0$ (KNO₃) and pH 8-9. The reduction of the complexes in each case is reversible and diffusion-controlled Cd²⁺ forms three mixed complex species, [Cd(amino acids)(pyridoxine)], [Cd(amino acids)(pyridoxine)₂] and [Cd(amino acids)₂(pyridoxine)], respectively.

MIXED-ligand complexes are important in analytical chemistry. Recently, a large number of such complexes have been studied polarographically. The mixed-ligand complexes of Cd with other ligands have been studied in our laboratory¹⁻³. A survey of literature reveals that simple complexes of Cd²⁺ with amino acids⁴ and with pyridoxine⁵ have been studied. However, polarographic studies on the mixed complexes of Cd²⁺ with amino acids (alanine, glycine, glutamic acid, serine and threonine) and pyridoxine have not been reported so far and hence, the title investigation.

Theoretical

For a complexation reaction,

where, *i* and *j* are stoichiometric numbers, X and Y are two different ligands and charges have been ignored for simplicity. The overall stability constant β_{ij} , for the reaction is given by,

$$\beta_{ij} = \frac{\beta_{MX_iY_j}}{[M][X]^i[Y]^j} \quad (2)$$

According to Schaap and McMasters, mixed-ligand complex formation should be preferred over simple complexes whenever the concentration of the ligands involved are such that the products of the formation constants for the simple complexes and the concentration of the ligand raised to the appropriate power are approximately equal, *i.e.*

$$\beta_{MX_i} [X]^i = \beta_{MY_j} [Y]^j \quad (3)$$

$F_o[X]$ function of the DeFord and Hume method may be extended to give a new function,

$$F_{o0}[X, Y] = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{0.4343nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_o} \right]$$

where *n*, *F*, *R* and *T* have the same meaning as in

the Nernst equation, I_M and I_o are the diffusion current constants of the uncomplexed and complex metallic ions, respectively. This expression can be written in the form (assuming three bidentate ligands),

$$F_{o0}[X, Y] = \{ \beta_{o0} + \beta_{o1}[Y] + \beta_{o2}[Y]^2 + \beta_{o3}[Y]^3 \} [X]^0 + \{ \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}[Y] + \beta_{12}[Y]^2 \} [X] + \{ \beta_{20} + \beta_{21}[Y] \} [X]^2 + \{ \beta_{30} \} [X]^3 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or, } F_{o0}[X, Y] = A + B[X] + C[X]^2 + D[X]^3 \quad (6)$$

where, for a given value of Y, A, B, C and D are constant having values defined in equation (5).

The concentration of one ligand is kept constant while that of the other is varied. In practice, Y is kept constant and X is varied. The other functions are

$$F_{10}[X, Y] = \left[\frac{F_{o0} - A}{[X]} \right] = B + C[X] + D[X]^2$$

$$F_{20}[X, Y] = \left[\frac{F_{10} - B}{[X]} \right] = C + D[X]$$

$$\text{and } F_{30}[X, Y] = \left[\frac{F_{20} - C}{[X]} \right] = D$$

With the help of two values of B at two concentrations the overall stability constants β_{11} , β_{12} and β_{21} may be calculated.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Pyridoxine and amino acids were used as complexing agents. Potassium nitrate was used as supporting electrolyte to maintain the ionic strength constant. A 0.004% gelatin was added to suppress the maxima. pH of all the solutions was maintained at 8-9, with a Elico LI-120 digital pH meter. Purified nitrogen was passed through the solution to

remove oxygen. Polarograms of the solution were taken using a manual polarograph. Saturated calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics; $m=1.96 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=4.05 \text{ s}$ per drop and $h_{\text{corr}}=40.0 \text{ cm}$ (at $303 \pm 1 \text{ K}$ in 0.1 M KNO_3 in open circuit).

Results

The formation constants of simple systems were calculated with the help of DeFord and Hume⁶ method, before the study of mixed-ligand systems. The conditions used corresponded as closely as possible to those for the mixed systems. The values of formation constants of simple systems are presented in Table 1, which are in good agreement with values in the literature^{4,5}.

The mixed complexes were studied by keeping the concentration of the weaker ligand (pyridoxine) constant at two different values while varying the concentration of amino acids in each case. The free ligand concentration for each system has been calculated with the help of pH of the solution, pK

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT FOR SIMPLE COMPLEXES

Systems	$\log \beta_{01}$	$\log \beta_{02}$	$\log \beta_{03}$
Pyrido	1.40	2.34	—
Ala	4.20	7.30	9.80
Gly	4.18	7.20	9.95
Glu	4.30	7.40	10.10
Ser	4.00	7.10	9.30
Threo	4.00	6.70	9.10

values and amount of the ligand. The pK values of amino acids were calculated⁷ at $303 \pm 1 \text{ K}$. In each case a single well defined wave was obtained. The plots of E_{a_2} vs $\log i/(i_a - i)$ were linear with slope of $30 \pm 2 \text{ mV}$, showing that the two-electron reduction is reversible. The direct proportionality of the diffusion current to the effective height of the mercury column indicated that the reduction is entirely diffusion-controlled.

The functions F_{00} , F_{10} , F_{20} and F_{30} were calculated by the method of Schaap and Mc-Masters⁸. The functions A, B, C, and D were calculated by Leden's graphical extrapolation method⁹. The F_{1j} function for only one system are given (Tables 2 and 3) for the sake of brevity.

TABLE 2—DATA AND RESULTS FOR Cd-ALANINATE-PYRIDOXINATE SYSTEM

[Pyridoxinate] = 0.04 M, $(E_{1/2})_M = -0.589 \text{ V vs SCE}$

$[X] \times 10^4 \text{ M}$	$\Delta E_{1/2}$	$\log \frac{I_M}{I_D}$	$F_{00} \times 10^{-3}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-4}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-7}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-9}$	$F_{00} \text{ (Calcd.)} \times 10^{-3}$	$\Delta F \%$
1.05	0.022	0.0010	0.05	2.91	1.82	—	0.06	+10.6
2.51	0.031	0.0020	0.11	3.37	2.57	6.92	0.11	± 0.00
5.05	0.041	0.0035	0.23	4.15	2.83	8.58	0.23	± 0.00
9.64	0.053	0.0040	0.59	5.83	3.92	8.54	0.58	-0.85
25.50	0.077	0.0045	3.68	14.35	4.56	8.48	3.69	+0.24
35.80	0.087	0.0065	7.96	22.17	5.43	8.47	7.98	+0.25
50.54	0.098	0.0077	18.54	36.64	6.71	8.53	18.51	-0.14
72.10	0.110	0.0087	46.60	64.60	8.58	8.58	46.36	-0.52
102.00	0.122	0.0098	117.15	114.83	10.99	8.42	118.08	+0.79
150.00	0.136	0.0112	343.49	228.98	15.08	8.46	345.92	+0.53

A = 2.35, B = 2.72×10^4 , C = 2.4×10^7 , D = 8.51×10^9 .

TABLE 3—DATA AND RESULTS FOR Cd-ALANINATE-PYRIDOXINATE SYSTEM

[Pyridoxinate] = 0.2 M, $(E_{1/2})_M = 0.589 \text{ V vs SCE}$

$[X] \times 10^4 \text{ M}$	$\Delta E_{1/2}$	$\log \frac{I_M}{I_D}$	$F_{00} \times 10^{-3}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-3}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-7}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-9}$	$F_{00} \text{ (Calcd.)} \times 10^{-3}$	$\Delta F \%$
0.50	0.041	0.0018	0.23	1.68	5.48	—	0.22	-4.40
2.55	0.052	0.0030	0.54	1.54	5.11	—	0.55	+0.87
5.01	0.060	0.0052	1.00	1.71	5.93	8.56	1.00	± 0.00
9.89	0.070	0.0060	2.16	2.04	6.34	8.45	2.16	± 0.00
25.27	0.088	0.0077	8.62	3.35	7.69	8.65	8.59	-0.35
34.20	0.095	0.0088	14.77	4.28	8.38	8.42	14.80	+0.20
50.30	0.105	0.0120	32.02	6.34	9.79	8.53	31.96	-0.19
71.50	0.115	0.0135	69.11	9.65	11.52	8.42	69.38	+0.39
102.00	0.126	0.0150	161.07	15.78	14.09	8.42	161.85	+0.48
151.16	0.139	0.0188	439.88	29.09	18.31	8.48	440.37	+0.11

$$*\Delta F(\%) = \frac{100}{F_{00}(\text{exp.})} \times [F_{00}(\text{calcd.}) - F_{00}(\text{exp.})].$$

A = 14.8, B = 1.41×10^6 , C = 5.5×10^7 , D = 8.48×10^9 .

The stability constants $\log \beta_{11}$ and $\log \beta_{12}$ were evaluated from the two values of B, the two values of C gave two values for β_{21} in good agreement with each other. The $\log \beta_{20}$ agree well with the mean value of $\log D$. The results are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANT OF MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES OF Cd²⁺ WITH AMINO ACIDS AND PYRIDOXINE

Systems	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
Cd-ala-Pyrido.	5.30	6.33	8.25
Cd-Gly-Pyrido.	5.20	6.26	8.35
Cd-Glu-Pyrido.	5.35	6.18	8.40
Cd-Ser-Pyrido.	5.05	6.00	7.98
Cd-Threo-Pyrido.	5.00	5.80	7.75

Discussion

The stability of ternary complexes can be explained with the help of Schemes 1-4. The tendency to add pyridoxinate to [Cd(pyridoxinate)] and [Cd(amino acids)] can be compared. The $\log K$ values are (0.94, 1.10), (0.94, 1.02), (0.94, 1.05), (0.94, 1.05) and (0.94, 1.00) for Cd-alanine-pyridoxinate, Cd-glycinate-pyridoxinate, Cd-glutamate-pyridoxinate, Cd-serinate-pyridoxinate and Cd-threoninate-pyridoxinate systems, respectively, and show that the mixed-ligand complexation is favoured. The $\log K$ values for the addition of amino acids to

Scheme 3. Cd-glutamate-pyridoxinate system.

Scheme 4. Cd-serinate-pyridoxinate system.

Scheme 1. Cd-alanine-pyridoxinate system.

Scheme 5. Cd-threoninate-pyridoxinate system.

Scheme 2. Cd-glycinate-pyridoxinate system.

[Cd(pyridoxinate)_n], [Cd(pyridoxinate)(amino acids)] and [Cd(amino acids)_n] are (3.99, 2.95 and 2.50), (3.92, 3.15 and 2.75), (3.84, 3.05 and 2.70), (3.66, 2.93 and 2.20) and (3.46, 2.75 and 2.40) for Cd-alanine-pyridoxinate, Cd-glycinate-pyridoxinate, Cd-glutamate-pyridoxinate, Cd-serinate-pyridoxinate and Cd-threoninate-pyridoxinate systems, respectively. This shows that the addition of amino acids is preferred to a weaker ligand (pyridoxine). The tendency to add amino acids to [Cd(pyridoxinate)] and [Cd(amino acids)] can also be compared. The $\log K$ values are (3.90, 3.20), (3.80, 3.02), (3.95, 3.10), (3.65, 3.10) and (3.60, 2.70) for all the systems

and show that formation of the mixed complexes is favoured by an amount corresponding to that product predicted by the statistical factor.

The stabilities of simple and mixed complexes can be compared by measuring the disproportionation constant K^D for the equilibria.

Statistically¹⁰ the concentration $[\text{Cd}(\text{amino acids})(\text{pyridoxine})]$ should be $[2\text{Cd}(\text{amino acids})_2]$ or $[2\text{Cd}(\text{pyridoxine})_2]$, so the values of the K^D should be $0.25=10^{-0.60}$. However, the observed values are found to be $10^{-0.96}$, $10^{-0.86}$, $10^{-0.96}$, $10^{-0.66}$ and $10^{-0.96}$ for Cd-alaninate-pyridoxinate, Cd-glycinate-pyridoxinate, Cd-glutamate-pyridoxinate, Cd-serinate-pyridoxinate and Cd-threoninate-pyridoxinate systems, respectively. These values are smaller than 0.25 which account for the stability of the mixed complexes.

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